

Open Journal Systems System Installation Considerations

0. introduction

Open Journal Systems is mainly used for publishing open source journals, including functions such as submission, review, and publishing.

There are multiple parts of the installation process that require special operations, and this article is only for record purposes. It includes version selection, environment configuration, post installation adjustment, error handling, etc.

1. Version selection

The installation version needs to be downloaded from the PKP official website. As of September 2023, the most stable version is version 3.3.0-15, and it is not recommended to install version 3.4. x. Each version has specific server, PHP, and database version requirements, and unknown versions are a lot of trouble.

2. Environmental configuration

Based on Open Journal Systems 3.3.0-15, after testing, both IIS10 server and Apache 2.4 server can operate normally. Nginx will report a large number of errors after enabling pseudo static, so it is not recommended to use.

Based on Open Journal Systems 3.3.0-15, it is recommended to use php7.3. After testing, versions PHP 7.3 to PHP 8.2 can run normally.

The database version requires a MySQL version greater than 5.6. After testing, it is recommended to use MySQL 8.0+ and connect using MySQL

In addition, PHP also needs to install multiple extensions, among which the necessary extension components are: intl, curl, mbstring, openssl, xml, and gettext. Be sure to ensure that the above extension components are turned on before installation.

3. Adjustment after installation

Since versions of Open Journal Systems after 3.0.0 support the install wizard installation, there is no need to manually configure the config.inc.php file. However, in order to ensure the normal operation of the software and enable error detection in case of errors, please also enable error display in config.inc.php.

```
; Display an error message when something goes wrong.  
display_errors = On
```

4.error handling

Q: Display a blank page after logging in to the administrator account

A: Blank pages are usually caused by PHP code running errors. Please check if the error display in config.inc.php is enabled.

Q: Error SSL certificate reported after login: unable to get local issuer certificate

A: There is no universal PEM format certificate configured for curl. Please download the latest version of the certificate according to the following link and configure the curl certificate address in php.ini.

Q: Error cURL error 77: error setting certificate verify locations after installing the universal PEM certificate

A: PHP does not have permission to access your PEM certificate. You can consider resetting the access permissions for the service or placing the PEM certificate in the root directory of the website.

PS: Remember to synchronize and modify the content in php.ini, but for security reasons, it is not recommended that you place the certificate in the root directory of the website.

Q: Fatal error: Call to undefined function bindtextdomain when starting the backend workflow panel

A: PHP does not install the gettext extension, just add the semicolon before gettext in PHP. ini; Just remove it.